

LINGUISTIC FEATURES AND FUNCTIONS OF COLLOQUIAL WORDS

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Abstract:

This article deals with the issue of linguistic features and functions of colloquial words in English language. Colloquial words play an important role in linguistics, the reason is that every person use them in their daily life for communicating with other people. People use colloquial words more than any other types of linguistic words. Due to the fact that, their shortened and simple forms are very easy for using in communication for people.

Key words: linguistics, colloquial words, function, feature, usage, analysing, slang, metaphorical implication, ironic implication, jargon, casual terms, idioms and shortened phrases, distinguishing linguistic feature;

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Before analysing the features and functions of colloquial words in linguistics, we should have knowledge about the notion of colloquial word. The informal spoken English style is typified by the use of colloquial language. It is important to differentiate between non-literary colloquialisms that are part of sub-standard English vocabulary and literary (standard) colloquial terms as components of Standard English.

The term literary colloquial is used to denote the vocabulary used by educated people in the course of ordinary conversation or when writing letters to intimate friends. The sphere of communication of literary colloquial words also includes the printed page, which shows that the term “colloquial” is somewhat inaccurate [1; 224]. Any person utilizes colloquial words everyday life without paying any attention. People tend to use more simple and short sentences and words. Colloquial words have also types. Colloquial vocabulary embraces common colloquial vocabulary and special colloquial vocabulary: slang, jargonisms, professionalisms, dialectal words, slang and vulgar words.

Literary colloquial terms are more like to neutral terms in terms of etymology and structure than they are to literary-bookish units, although they often have greater emotional connotations. They are created using common word-formative patterns (phrasal verbs and nouns, contraction). Several of them are very common: touchy, make-up, put up, birdie and others.

Terms that are not literary colloquialisms include vulgarisms, jargon, slang, and professionalism. Very casual terms that are not appropriate for dignified use are called slang. These are substandard emotive words that can be used in place of more modern, standard vocabulary terms [4, 139].

Generally speaking, they have ironic colouring and metaphorical implications: attic (“head”), beans (“money”), saucers (“eyes”). Such words are easily understood by all native

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speakers, because they are not specific for any social or professional group. This is the one of linguistics features of colloquial words. Additionally, A great deal of colloquial language is very emotive and image-laden. For instance, there are several contextual subjective modal interpretations that the interjections oops, oh, gosh, wow, and alas can convey, including joy, ecstasy, disappointment, resentment, and adoration.

There myriad linguistic features of colloquial words. For example, they serve as a basic for colloquial style. This style differs from others according to some typical peculiarities, such as colloquial words often used in dialogues and people want to speak less and concrete. One of the linguistic feature is that they are very emotional. People use them in their daily life more than other type of expressing emotion.

As far as the functions of colloquial words is concerned, the colloquial language are frequently employed in informal talks is an important feature to consider. This makes it an excellent literary device for the discussion between your characters. Another thing to keep in mind regarding colloquial phrases is that they are general terms that are restricted by the contexts in which they are employed. It is imperative that you evaluate the usage of colloquial terms in your work before using them. For instance, the majority of people in America refer to elevators as "elevators." But in Britain, the word "lift" is more frequently employed.

This will also give the discourse a more genuine and engaging tone. Additionally, you might employ common colloquial terms to make your wordplay more intricate. All things considered, it always pays to be aware of a word's colloquial counterpart since it gives your conversation and storyline more nuance. Among other informal words, colloquialisms are the least exclusive: they are used by everybody, and their sphere of communication is comparatively wide [3; 13].

In conclusion, people of all ages and social classes use colloquial terms, but they differ slightly. Playwrights and authors frequently utilize colloquial language in their works. While colloquialism usually tends to intrude, most authors purposefully employ figures of speech to enhance their writing. Authors purposefully employ colloquialism to give their writing a modern feel and to give it a feeling of realism.

Colloquial word have many distinguishing features, for example, the vocabulary of the colloquial language consists of commonly used words (work, read, book, house) and colloquial words (gonna, wanna, trash, cheers) and this provide listener concrete and short information. The reason is that there are rarely used terminology or abstract concepts. However, people use many idioms and shortened phrases in their speeches. This is also one of the distinguishing linguistic peculiarities of the colloquial words.

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